

On the Physico-Chemical Properties of Electrodialysed Gels of Silica, Alumina, Ferric Hydroxide and their Mixture. Part I. Ion Exchange.

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Recent investigations carried out in this laboratory showed that the clay fraction in laterite soils exceed 40%. Their agricultural properties, however, do not at all correspond to those of heavy soils. Of the various investigations concerning the silica sesquioxide ratio, reference should be made to those of Mattson (First International Congress of Soil Science, Vol. 2, p. 199) on the adsorption of cations and anions by soil colloidal materials and to those of Ghosh and Bhattacharyya (*Soil Science*, 1930, **29**, 311) on the adsorption of calcium and phosphate ions, as those investigations have a bearing on the present one.

Anderson (*J. Agric. Res.*, 1929, **38**, 565) has recently studied the influence of substitution of cations on the various physical properties with varying $\text{SiO}_2/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 + \text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ ratios of the soil colloids. The relation between the experimental results of these investigators and those of ours will be discussed later. As stated in a previous publication (Ghosh and Bhattacharyya, *loc. cit.*) mixed gels of silica + alumina and silica + ferric oxide as obtained by mutual precipitation may have properties comparable resulting in some respects those of the soil colloids.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Silica Gel.—It was prepared by hydrolysing pure silicon tetrachloride in a large volume of water and then adding an excess of ammonia. The gel obtained was then electrodialysed in a 220 volt current for a long time with a constant flow of conductivity water until there was no trace of ammonia and chlorine in the cathode and anode respectively. The presence of ammonia was tested with the help of Nessler's reagent and that of chlorine determined electrometrically (Bell and Doisy, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1920, **44**, 45). The electrodialysed gel was then filtered and dried in an electric oven kept at a constant temperature of 34° until the weight of the dry gel was found constant.

Aluminium Hydroxide Gel.—Ammonia was added in excess to a solution of pure aluminium chloride in water. The gel of aluminium hydroxide was then electro dialysed in exactly the same way as before until there was no trace of chlorine and ammonia. The electro dialysed gel after filtration was dried as before.

Ferric Hydroxide Gel.—Excess of ammonia was added to a solution of pure ferric chloride in water. The jelly-like mass so obtained was electro dialysed, filtered and dried to constant weight as in the previous cases.

Preparation of mixed Gels of (a) Silica and Aluminium hydroxide, (b) Silica and Ferric hydroxide by Mutual Precipitation.— SiCl_4 was hydrolysed in a large volume of water containing AlCl_3 or ferric chloride in solution, and then excess of ammonia was added to obtain a precipitate of both in presence of each other. The jelly-like mass was then electro dialysed, filtered and dried to constant weight as before.

The percentage of SiO_2 and Al_2O_3 in the ignited sample was estimated.

TABLE I.

Mixture No.	Composition.		Ratio.
I	SiO_2 , 72%	Al_2O_3 , 28%	$\text{SiO}_2/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 = 4.37$
II	„ 44	„ 56	„ = 1.33
III	„ 58	Fe_2O_3 , 42	$\text{SiO}_2/\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3 = 3.68$
IV	„ 28	„ 72	„ = 1.04

Saturation of Samples prepared with NaCl, KCl, CaCl_2 and MgCl_2 .—Normal solutions of NaCl, KCl, and MgCl_2 were first prepared.

Four stoppered conical flasks, each containing about 5 gms. of Fe_2O_3 were shaken with 50 c. c. of normal solution of NaCl, KCl, CaCl_2 and MgCl_2 in a shaking machine for about 8 hours. The suspensions in different electrolytes were then kept over-night. After removing the supernatant liquids, 50 c. c. solutions of normal NaCl, KCl, MgCl_2 , CaCl_2 were again introduced into the flasks as before and shaken again for about 6 hours.

The suspensions were then filtered and washed with water until the concentration of chlorine ion in the filtrate was 1×10^{-5} chlorine or less. The concentration of chlorine ion was tested electrometrically (cf. Bert, *J. Agric. Sci.*, 1929, **91**, 533).

Other gel samples were also treated exactly in the same way as this one.

The samples were dried to constant weight at 34°; moisture present in the samples was determined in each case and was taken into reconsideration in calculating the amount of ions adsorbed.

Estimation of Na, K, Ca, Mg in the Saturated Samples.

Each of the saturated substances was extracted with $N\text{-NH}_4\text{Cl}$. Sodium was estimated in the extracted solution gravimetrically by the magnesium uranyl acetate method as recommended by Kahlanc (*Bull. Soc. chim. France*, 1930, **47-48**, 4).

Potassium was estimated colorimetrically by precipitating it as potassium chloroplatinate (Hill, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1903, **25**, 990).

Calcium was precipitated as Ca-oxalate and titrated with $N/100$ KMnO_4 . An improvement in the technique was introduced by using frittered jena-glass filter and filtrating directly the precipitate adhering to the filter after washing with permanganate.

Magnesium was estimated colorimetrically. It was separated as magnesium ammonium phosphate and the latter converted into phosphomolybdate which in turn was treated with the hydroquinone and carbonate-sulphite solution of Bell and Doisy (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1920, **44**, 55) and the resulting colour matched against a standard.

Blank estimations of Na, K, Ca, and Mg in very dilute solutions of their chloride gave the following limits of error:—Na, ± 2.5 %; K + Mg, ± 5 %; Ca, ± 3 %.

A portion of the saturated samples was shaken with an excess of a saturated solution of magnesium nitrate for about 6 hours, filtered and washed several times with saturated magnesium nitrate solution. Chlorine was then estimated electrometrically (Bert, *loc. cit.*) in the filtrate. Absolutely pure magnesium nitrate was used in all these cases.

In calculating amount of adsorption, the water of hydration was taken into consideration. In our experiments the materials after saturation with the different salt solutions were washed until the Cl^- -ion concentration was less than 1×10^{-5} . The gels in the wet state never contained more than 66% water; on this basis the Cl^- -ion in the water of hydration per gram of dried gel comes to about 2×10^{-6} . From the data it will be observed that this amount is negligibly small compared with the amount of Cl^- -ion found by exchange from the

different gels. Also the amount of cations as obtained by exchange is of the order of 1×10^{-4} . Thus the amount of positive and negative ions in the water of hydration do not appreciably affect our results.

Experimental results are given in Tables II to VI.

TABLE IIa.

Exchangeable cations.

Saturated with.	SiO ₂		Al ₂ O ₃		Fe ₂ O ₃	
	M. equiv./g. of the substance.	M. equiv./g. mol. of the substance.	M. equiv./g. of the substance.	M. equiv./g. mol. of the substance.	M. equiv./g. of the substance.	M. equiv./g. mol. of the substance.
NaCl	0.28	16.86	0.23	23.94	0.05	8.61
KCl	0.09	5.58	0.09	8.99	0.07	11.18
CaCl ₂	0.11	7.02	0.07	7.18	0.12	19.29
MgCl ₂	0.21	12.86	0.05	4.94	0.10	16.27

TABLE IIb.

Samples used (1 g.) are same as in Table I.

Saturated with.	Mixture (I)		Mixture (II)		Mixture (III)		Mixture (IV)	
	M. equiv./g. of the substance.	* Exchangeable cations.	M. equiv./g. of the substance.	* Exchangeable cations.	M. equiv./g. of the substance.	* Exchangeable cations.	M. equiv./g. of the substance.	* Exchangeable cations.
NaCl	0.482	0.27	0.27	0.25	0.271	0.18	0.31	0.12
KCl	0.28	0.09	0.13	0.09	0.19	0.08	0.13	0.08
CaCl ₂	0.15	0.10	0.15	0.09	0.25	0.11	0.13	0.12
MgCl ₂	0.33	0.17	0.31	0.12	0.23	0.16	0.49	0.13

* Calculated from the law of additive mixtures given in m. equiv. per g. of the substance.

TABLE IIIa.

Exchangeable *Cl*-ion.

Saturated with.	SiO ₂		Al ₂ O ₃		Fe ₂ O ₃	
	M. equiv./g. of the substance.	M. equiv./g. mol. of the substance.	M. equiv./g. of the substance.	M. equiv./g. mol. of the substance.	M. equiv./g. of the substance.	M. equiv./g. mol. of the substance.
NaCl	Nil	Nil	0'06	6'18	0'02	3'43
KCl	"	"	0'06	6'18	0'02	3'43
CaCl ₂	"	"	0'06	6'18	0'035	5'62
MgCl ₂	"	"	0'06	6'18	0'034	5'44

TABLE IIIb.

Samples used are same as in Table I.

Saturated with.	Mixture (I)		Mixture (II)		Mixture (III).		Mixture (IV)	
	M. equiv./g. of the substance.	*Calc. value of anion exchangeable.	M. equiv./g. of the substance.	*Calc. value of anion exchangeable.	M. equiv./g. of the substance.	*Calc. value of anion exchangeable.	M. equiv./g. of the substance.	*Calc. value of anion exchangeable.
NaCl	0'0030	1'09	0'018	3'30	0'0059	2'25	0'024	5'32
KCl	0'0029	1'06	0'010	2'00	0'0050	1'90	0'020	4'44
CaCl ₂	0'0028	1'02	0'013	2'34	0'0063	2'40	0'017	3'82
MgCl ₂	0'0028	1'02	0'013	2'40	0'0055	2'10	0'023	5'05

* Value of anion exchangeable per g. mol. of sesquioxide, taking the sesquioxide as the only adsorbing material.

TABLE IV.**

Silica powder.

3'3087 gms. of the powder was suspended in 250 c.c. water (Sp. C. $1'5 \times 10^{-6}$ at 30°).

pH of suspension = 5'6 (by Folin colorimeter)

= 5'5 (by quinhydrone electrode)

Sp. C. of suspension at 31'5° = $1'88 \times 10^{-6}$ mhos.

pH of supernatant liquid = 6'0 (by Folin colorimeter)

= 6'1 (by quinhydrone electrode).

Sp. C. of supernatant liquid at 31° = $1'88 \times 10^{-6}$ mhos.

TABLE V.**

Suspended silica gel.

Dilution.	pH by quinhydrone.	pH by colorimeter.	Sp. conductivity. $\times 10^5$
Pure	4.91	4.8-5.0	4.489
5 times	5.80	5.6-5.8	1.825
10	5.87	5.6-5.8	1.169
20	6.08	5.8-6.0	0.956

TABLE VI.**

Supernatant liquid of silica gel.

Dilution.	pH by quinhydrone.	pH by colorimeter.	Sp. conductivity $\times 10^5$.
Pure	5.41	5.2-5.4	4.489
5 times	6.00	5.8-6.0	1.500
10	6.10	6.0-6.2	1.096
20	6.10	6.0-6.2	0.742

DISCUSSION.

A portion of the silica gel purified by electro dialysis was kept in a flask. This was analysed after the experiments were finished (after 2 years) under the supervision of Prof. J. N. Mukherjee. The results will give an idea as to the purity of the gel prepared by us. This is of importance because the properties of colloidal precipitates are often dependent on the degree of purity as also on the method of precipitation.

In Tables IV, V and VI are given the pH and conductivity of silica powder, suspended silica gel and the supernatant liquid of the gel. As pointed out by Mukherjee, "The silica contained electrolytes which increased the specific conductivity of water from 1.6×10^{-6} to 4.5×10^{-5} ." When a chloride is titrated with an AgNO_3 solution, at the theoretical end-point the Cl-ion concentration becomes of the order of 1×10^{-5} ." Electro dialysis was stopped when the Cl-ion concentration in the gel and in the dialysate was of this order. Our gel, therefore,

** pH of conductivity water = 6.5 (by B.T.B.). Sp. conductivity of water = 1.6×10^{-6} . Measurements carried out at room temperature ($31^\circ - 32^\circ$).

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contained, after electrodialysis, the colloidal ions and gegenions and a small quantity of electrolyte, HCl, as is evident from its conductivity.

The possible anions on the surface of the silica gel are the hydroxyl and silicate ions. Structurally it may be represented as follows :—

The cations on the liquid side are only the equivalent amount of H^+ ions. Again on the surface of alumina and ferric hydroxide gels, there may be Al(OH)_2^+ , $\text{Al(OH)}''$ and Al''' ions and Fe(OH)_2^+ , $\text{Fe(OH)}''$ and Fe''' ions respectively, and also hydrogen ions. On the liquid side there are hydroxyl ions. Structurally :—

When excess of salt solution comes in contact with the silica gel the main possibilities are :—Primary adsorption of the anions of the salt on the surface, adsorption of equivalent amount of cations of the salt by electrical attraction, exchange of cations on the liquid side of the gel with those of the salt. Such adsorption and exchange process might also occur in case of alumina and ferric hydroxide; had exchange adsorption been the only process occurring, one would expect the adsorption of cations of the salt on the surface of silica gel and displacement of equivalent amount of H^+ ions out of the double layer into the liquid.

Besides ion-exchange and ion-adsorption, contact with neutral salt solution may change the structure of the electrodialysed gel. We have noted that during the process of electrodialysis, the gels are flocculated and form a stiff mass on the anode side of the middle chamber. This material can be redispersed by vigorous shaking. The nature of the gel is determined mainly by the cations in the outside layer. According to the Wiegner "If the cations present in soils are more highly hydrated as sodium and magnesium ions, the soil becomes converted into a dense impervious mass which on suspension in water subsides very slowly *i.e.*, coagulates with difficulty; but the more slightly hydrated ions the soil contains, as for instance potassium and calcium ions, the greater is its degree of coagulation."

In our experiments, the electro dialysed gels were first saturated with the chlorides of Na, K, Ca and Mg respectively, and the effect of leaching with pure water until the wash-liquid was free from Cl⁻ ion was studied. The cations retained by these well-washed gels were determined by ammonium chloride extraction as recommended by Mattson (*J. Agric. Sci.*, 1926, 33, 553) who showed that this process removed quantitatively the whole of the exchangeable bases and that the same amount was exchangeable by electro dialysis. Bradfield (*First Int. Congress, Soil Sci.*, 1928, 2, 264) has also confirmed this view. Hence we can assume that all bases exchangeable under the condition of our experiment were removed by the NH₄Cl extraction. Again absorbability of anions has been shown by Mukherjee (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 1, 173) to be in the order NO₃ > I > SO₄ > Cl. So the Mg(NO₃)₂ extraction in our experiments is expected to give all the exchangeable chlorine ions.

It will be observed from Tables II and III that there is no stoichiometric relationship between the exchangeable metal ions and chlorine ions. Silica yields by exchange considerable amount of cations but no Cl⁻ ions. Probably it does not adsorb any Cl⁻ ions which is due to the fact that "Silica has a strong capacity to absorb OH ions and to a much less extent other anions" and that in presence of water, the surface is saturated with OH ions.

Exchangeable Cl⁻ ions per g. of alumina, as shown in Table III, is approximately the same and is independent of the metal ion which formed the chloride. Adsorption of Cl⁻ ions is mainly due to the replacement of OH ions (as was evident from a rise in pH of the washed liquid). The same also applies in the case of ferric oxide gel, where the exchangeable Cl⁻ ion of the Na-saturated material is the same as that of the K-saturated material. Also the Ca and Mg-complexes again yield equivalent amounts of exchangeable Cl⁻ ions.

In the case of each of the silica sesquioxide mixtures the same amount of chlorine ions (shown in Table III) is obtained independent of the metal chloride used for exchange. Since silica does not adsorb Cl, this anion is evidently obtained from the sesquioxides present in the mixtures. This confirms the suggestion of Mattson (*loc. cit.*) that the adsorption of anions by soils is due to the presence of free sesquioxides in the soils. The data clearly show that the exchangeable quantities of anions increase with a decrease in the ratio of silica to sesquioxide as has been shown by Mattson for a wide range of soils. Columns (3, 5, 7 and 9) of Table IIIb give the exchangeable Cl⁻ ions per g. mol. taking

sesquioxides as the active adsorbing material. Pure alumina yields much larger amount of exchangeable chlorine ion than an equivalent of alumina in a silicate mixture. This shows that the presence of silica in the mixture has diminished the active adsorbing surface of alumina. This also holds good for the $\text{SiO}_2/\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ mixtures. Fig. 2 a, b show the effect of silica on the amount of Cl^- ions obtained by exchange from alumina and ferric hydroxide, when present in different proportions. In the case of $\text{SiO}_2/\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ mixture IV, however, Na- and K-saturated samples yield larger amounts of Cl^- ions than the Na- and K-saturated pure ferric hydroxide gel. Hence, silica at low percentage tends to increase the active adsorbing surface of the Na- and K-saturated ferric hydroxide gel. An explanation of such a peculiar behaviour has recently been put forward by Mattson (*Soil Sci.*, 1935, 39, 161).

It is found that in pure alumina, the exchangeable amount of cations is in the order $\text{Na} > \text{K} > \text{Ca} > \text{Mg}$. In ferric hydroxide, however, the milli-equivalents of Ca and Mg are almost the same and are practically double the milliequivalents of sodium or potassium per gram of the gel; we may therefore infer that for 1 g. of the material there is a definite number of points on the surface to which an exchangeable ion of Ca, Mg, Na or K can get fixed.

Gel composition.

Curves 1-4 refer respectively to Na, K, Ca and Mg saturated materials.

Cation exchange in case of silica sesquioxide gels is always greater than that calculated from the law of mixture, the maximum difference being observed in the case of magnesium saturated gel. This shows that exchange of bases in soils is mainly regulated by the presence of silica. As a matter of fact the amount of exchangeable Na in one g. of pure silica gel is the same as that in 1 g. of silica-alumina mixed gel containing only 0.44 g. of silica. It is also remarkable that whereas the amount of exchangeable metal ion from pure ferric hydroxide is small compared with silica, mixed gels of ferric oxide and silica yield more metal ions than pure silica itself. This indicates a great increase in the degree of dispersion of silica gel when precipitated with ferric hydroxide. Such is also the case with $\text{SiO}_2/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ mixtures. Fig. 1a and b show the relation between the composition of gels and exchangeable cation. It may be noted here that the amounts of exchangeable ions in these artificial gels are of the same order of magnitude as are noticed in the clay fractions of soils.

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A Note on the Constitution of the Reduction Product of Trichloromethylparaconic Acid.

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The reduction of trichloromethylparaconic acid (I) has been studied by Fittig and Miller (*Ber.*, 1887, 20, 3181; *Annalen*, 1889, 255, 43) and Meyers (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1902, 24, 525). They assign the formula (II) to the reduction product.

While studying the condensation of chloral with various acids, the present authors had occasion to prepare trichloromethylparaconic acid and reduce it. As a result of their work they consider the reduction product is a dibasic acid as represented in formula (III) and has not the structure (II) given by Fittig and Miller. This has been proved (a) by preparing from the reduction product diesters (IV and IVa),